

Clinical Study on Effectiveness of Vacuum Assisted Closure on Various Types of Wounds in Government General Hospital Kakinada – Retrospective Study

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Abstract:

Background: Vacuum-assisted closure employs the application of constant sub atmospheric pressure on the wound, which removes the excess fluid, reducing bacterial proliferation and infection, and enabling the wound to heal at the earliest.

Method: 50 (fifty) adult patients with different types of wounds were studied. A complete haemogram, random blood sugar, renal function test, CRP level, x-ray of the affected part, culture, and sensitivity of pus/discharge from ulcer wound dressing were utilized by medium-density polyvinyl alcohol (PVC). The applied negative pressure ranged from 100 mm Hg to >150 mm Hg.

Results: The site of injury was highest in leg 18 (36%) followed by foot 13 (26%) and least was around hip 1 (2%). The maximum size of wound was found in 5 (10%) it was 21-25 cms and least in 1 (2%) was 1-5 cms and maximum duration of healing was 21-25 days observed in 6 (12%) VAC pressure ranged from 100 mm Hg to > 150 mm Hg, 35 (70%) had excellent outcome of healing and 15 (30%) had good outcome of wound healing.

Conclusion: The VAS technique is efficient to heal the complicated wounds and ulcers. It is a promising alternative clinical method for various types of wound healing.

Keywords: vacuum-assisted closure, negative pressure, various types of wounds, dressing therapy, non-healing wound.

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Introduction

Large complicated wounds pose significant surgical problems. The duration of treatment is usually long-lasting and costly therapy for middle and lower socio-economic patients [1]. Bacterial infections negatively influence the patients general conditions, which leads to morbidity due to the development of sepsis and ends in amputation of infected organs and mortality too [2].

Negative pressure wound therapy is becoming a common treatment modality in many clinical settings since its efficacy was initially described by Moryk et al. in 1997.

Later, numerous studies have shown effectiveness of negative pressure wound therapy in chronic wounds, diabetic wounds, and pressure sores. The use of negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT) enables to obtain a reduction in bacterial infection and enhances early healing [3].

Vacuum-assisted closure employs the application of constant sub-atmospheric pressure on the

wound, which effectively removes excess interstitial fluid from the wound by reducing bacterial proliferation and infection [4].

Hence, an attempt was made to evaluate the different types of wounds in adult patients; their effectiveness was studied.

Material and Method

50 (fifty) adult patients (above 18 years) regularly visited the plastic surgery department of the government medical college hospital Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh 533001 were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Wounds with exposed bone and tendons, traumatic wounds, wounds with crust and debris, non-healing ulcers. The patients who gave their consent for study in writing were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Age below 18 years, fistula to organs or body cavities, untreated osteomyelitis, wounds with exposed blood vessels or organs,

malignant wounds, patients with haemorrhagic disorders, allergies to adhesive drapes, patients on anti-coagulants or platelet aggregation inhibitors.

Method:

The negative controlled pressure is uniformly applied to all tissues on the inner surface of the wound. The foam dressing was made to compress in response to the negative pressure. The entire wound site was enclosed using a Tegaderm / sterilized polythene cover/ cling drape / or sterile surgical glove. The suction catheter is connected to a vacuum-generating device and energized. The Syringe, mucus suction device, romovac, and pedal suction machine were systematically cleared of drainage and recharged with vacuum following at regular intervals. The pump delivered either continuous or intermittent pressures ranging from 50 to 125 mm Hg (adjustable up to 200 mm Hg). Intermittent delivery consisted of a seven-minute cycle of two minutes on, while the negative pressure was maintained. The ideal pressure setting was 125 mm Hg, but particularly painful chronic wounds such as chronic leg ulcers were managed with lower therapeutics. Pressure of 50 to 75 mm Hg plus large cavity wounds, such as acute traumatic wounds, as they produced copious amounts of exudates. The pressure was set to continuous for the first 48 hours, and the pressure was changed as required thereafter.

The measurement of wound surface was conducted by utilizing a plastic sheet imprinted with a grid pattern, which was placed over graph paper. The resulting imprints were carefully observed and recorded. A wound swab specimen was collected to perform a culture and sensitive test. If there was clean granulation tissue present above the wound

surface, bactigrass or Vaseline gauze was applied. It prevented the dressing from sticking to the wound surface and minimized bleeding when the dressing was removed, and the progress of healing in days was recorded.

The duration of the study was January 2014 to August 2015.

Statistical Analysis: Various sites of injury (wounds), size of wounds, and duration of therapy, VAC pressure application, and outcome of results were studied and classified with percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of male and female was 2:1.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Study of site of injury –

- Forearm: 2 right side, 2 left 4 (8%)
- Around hip 1 (2%) left
- Thigh: 2 right side, 8 left 10 (20%)
- Knee: 2 right 2 (4%)
- Leg: right 8, 10 left 18 (36%)
- Ankle: 2 right (4%)
- Foot: 7 right, 6 left, 13 (26%)

Table 2: study of size of various types of wounds – 1 (2%) 1-5 cm, 14 (28%) 6-10 cm, 23 (46%) 11-15 cm, 7 (14%) 16-20 cm, 5 (10%) 21-25 cm

Table 3: Study of duration of therapy – 2 (4%) 1-5 days 29 (58%) 6-10 cm, 13 (26%) 11-15 cm, 6 (12%) 21-25 cm

Table 4: VAC pressure applied in various wounds – 10 (20%) up to 100 mm of Hg, 5 (10%) 100-150 mm Hg, 35 (70%) > 150 mm Hg

Table 5: Study of outcomes of VAC therapy 35 (70%) excellent, 15 (30%) good Discussion.

Table 1: Study of site of injury (Total no. of patients: 50)

Site of injury	Right	Left	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Forearm	2	2	4	8
Around hip	0	1	1	2
Thigh	2	8	10	20
Knee	2	0	2	4
Leg	8	10	18	36
Ankle	2	0	2	4
Foot	7	6	13	26
Total	23	27	50	100

Figure 1: Study of site of injury

Table 2: Study of size of various types of wounds

Size of wounds (cms)	No. of cases (50)	Percentage (%)
1 – 2	1	2
6 – 10	14	28
11 – 15	23	46
16 – 20	7	14
21 – 25	5	10
Total	50	100

Figure 2: Study of size of various types of wounds

Table 3: Study of duration of therapy

Duration of therapy	No. of cases (50)	Percentage (%)
1 – 5	2	4
6 – 10	29	58
11 – 15	13	26
16 – 20	0	--
21 – 25	6	12
Total	50	100

Figure 3: Study of duration of therapy

Table 4: VAC pressure applied in various wounds

VAC pressure	No. of cases (50)	Percentage (%)
Up to 100mm of Hg	10	20
100-150 mm of Hg	5	10
> 150 mm of Hg	35	70
Total	50	100

Figure 4: VAC pressure applied in various wounds

Table 5: Outcome of VAC Therapy

Wound healing	No. of cases (50)	Percentage (%)
Excellent	35	70
Good	15	30
Poor	0	--

Figure 5: Outcome of VAC Therapy

Discussion

Present study of effectiveness of VAC on various types of wounds in patients attending government general hospital Kakinada. In the study of site of injury, the highest site was leg 18 (36%), followed by foot 13 (26%), and the least site was around hip 1 (2%) (Table 1). In the study of the size of various wounds, the maximum size was 21-25 cms in 5 (10%), followed by 16-26 cm in 7 (14%), and the least was 1-5 cms in 1 (2%) patient (Table 2). In the study of duration of therapy, the highest duration was 21–25 days in 6 (12%) patients, and the least duration was 1–5 days in 2 (4%) patients (Table 3). In the VAC pressure application study, the highest VAC pressure was >150 mm Hg in 35 (70%) patients and the least was up to 100 mm Hg in 10 (20%) cases (Table 4). The outcome of VAC therapy was 35 (70%) excellent, and 15 (30%) had a good outcome of healing (Table 5). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7]. Wound healing is a complete complex and involves multiple molecular processes, including angiogenesis, granular tissue formation, re-epithelialization, and wound contraction (in secondary healing). Therefore, an effective treatment that improves wound healing is unlikely to involve only one or two of these [8].

Previously, it was reported that VAC wound healing showed improved removal of oedema fluid, increased blood flow, granulation tissue formation, and bacterial clearance in wounds. These effects were attributed to the negative pressure generated by the device without insights into molecular mechanisms, but more recent in vitro studies have shown that the presence of negative pressure can cause cellular strain and micro-deformations on the wound. Further, more 5–20% of strains on cells could promote cellular proliferation and molecular changes [9]. It is also reported that mechanical forces could lead to changes in endothelial morphology, resulting in endothelial cell proliferation, increased capillary density, and budding. The wounds had increased vessel formation by quantified micro vessel densities in the tissues [10]. As the healing progressed, these vessels decreased in number, but wounds had larger caliber mature blood vessels [11].

The VAC foam with negative pressure resulted in increased growth factor production, improved angiogenesis, collagen deposition, and earlier wound organization, which enhanced early healing of wounds, probably reflected by the combined effects of negative pressure and the presence of the granular foam rather than negative pressure alone.

Summary and Conclusion

VAC has been proven to be a reliable method of treating a variety of infected wounds hence VAC

has revolutionised wound care because it greatly increases the rate of granulation tissue formation and lowers bacterial infection to accelerate wound healing. The present study demands further pharmacological, environmental, genetic and patho-physiological study because exact molecular mechanism of VAC is not well understood.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location, small number of patients and lack of latest techniques we have limited finding and results.

This research work was approved by the ethical committee of government medical college hospital Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh-533001.

References

1. Moues CM, VOS MC: Bacterial load in relation to vacuum-assisted closure wound therapy. *Journal wound repair Regen* 2004, 12; 11-17.
2. Mulliner T, Mrkonji CL: The use of negative pressure to promote the healing tissue defects *Br. J. plast. Sura.* 1997, 50; 194-99.
3. Crestis, Ouaisi M: Advantages of vacuum assisted closure on healing wounds associated with omentoplasty after abdominoperineal excision *world J. Surg. Oncol.* 2008, 6; 136-139.
4. Fleischmann W, Streckar W: Vacuum sealing as treatment of soft tissue damage in open fractures. *J. Unfall Chirurg* 1993, 96 (3); 488-92.
5. Fleischmann W, Beaker U: Vacuum sealing indication, technique, and results *Eur. J. Orthop. Surg. Traumatol.* 1995, 5 (1); 37-40.
6. Valencia IC, Galabella A: Chronic venous insufficiency and venous leg ulceration *J. Am. Acad. Dermatol.* 2001, 44; 401-21.
7. Stadelmann WK, Digenis AD: physiology and healing dynamics of chronic coetaneous wounds *Am. J. Surg.* 1998, 176; 265-385.
8. Greene AK, Puder M, Roy R: Micro deformational wound therapy: effects on angiogenesis and matrix metalloproteinases in chronic wounds *Ann. Plast Surg.* 2006, 56; 418-22.
9. Saxena V, Hwang CW: Vacuum-assisted closure, microdeformation of wounds, and cell proliferations *plast reconstruction surg.* 2004, 114; 1086-96.
10. Chen SZ, Li J, Lixy: Effects of vacuum-assisted closure on wound micro circulation: an experimental study *Assian J. Surg.* 2005, 28; 211-17.
11. Galiana R, Tepper O: Topical vascular endothelial growth factor accelerates diabetic wound angiogenesis *Am. J. Pathol.* 2004, 164; 1935-47.